

**PHARMACEUTICALS AND NATURAL REMEDIES FOR
HYPOTENSION****Rakhmonkulova Nargizakhon Bakhromjon kizi****Kokand University Andijan Branch****Student of DI 25-34 group****Mirzamansurova Robiyahon****robixon0512@gmail.com****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19543489>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 06th April 2026Accepted: 08th April 2026Online: 10th April 2026**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a classification of modern pharmaceuticals and natural herbal remedies considered effective in the treatment of arterial hypotension. It analyzes the pharmacological properties of drugs that increase blood pressure and their mechanisms of action on the human body. Furthermore, the study highlights the clinical significance of safe and efficient phytopreparations used to manage low blood pressure. The provided data serves as an essential practical guide for selecting optimal pharmacotherapy methods for patients suffering from hypotension.

Introduction.**Relevance of the topic:**

Today, arterial hypotension is becoming an important not only medical, but also social problem, as it directly affects the reduction of working capacity and deterioration of the quality of life. In modern medicine, the demand for drugs with high efficiency and minimal side effects in the treatment of hypotension, especially those based on natural components, is increasing. A comprehensive analysis of synthetic and natural remedies allows us to develop individual and safe treatment methods for patients. Therefore, the study of pharmaceutical and natural possibilities for eliminating hypotension is one of the urgent tasks of modern pharmacotherapy.

Research objective:

The main objective of this study is to conduct a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of modern pharmaceutical drugs and natural remedies used in the treatment of arterial hypotension and to scientifically substantiate the mechanisms of their influence on the human body. It is also intended to provide recommendations for the development of complex treatment methods that are safe and have a high therapeutic effect in eliminating hypotension.

The main factors in the development of arterial hypotension are a decrease in vascular tone, a decrease in cardiac output, a decrease in the activity of the autonomic nervous system, or a lack of fluid in the body. Therefore, the selection of agents used to treat hypotension should be focused on its pathophysiology. Drugs normalize arterial pressure by narrowing the vessels, increasing the force of cardiac contraction, or increasing the volume of circulating blood.

Among pharmaceutical agents, adrenomimetics are one of the most effective groups. Midodrine constricts peripheral vessels by stimulating alpha-1 receptors and is one of the first-choice drugs for orthostatic hypotension. Phenylephrine, by constricting muscle and skin vessels, quickly restores arterial pressure. Norepinephrine, as a strong vasoconstrictor, is used only in severe cases, including shock and collapse, in intensive care.

Cardiotonic agents - dopamine and dobutamine - increase cardiac contractility and increase cardiac output. Moderate doses of dopamine significantly increase blood pressure, and dobutamine is used especially in hypotension associated with heart failure. Mineralocorticoids - fludrocortisone - increase the amount of fluid in the body by retaining sodium and are effective in restoring blood pressure. In cases of pressure drop due to hypovolemia, infusion solutions: 0.9% sodium chloride and Ringer's solutions restore the body's fluid balance and quickly improve hemodynamics. Natural remedies are more often used for mild to moderate hypotension. Adaptogenic plants - ginseng, eleutherococcus, radiola rozovaya (golden root) and limonnik - enhance the activity of the central nervous system, increase the overall tone of the body and have a normalizing effect on arterial pressure. Ginseng ginsenosides activate cell metabolism and increase energy metabolism, while eleutherococcus stimulates the production of noradrenaline. Radiola rozovaya improves the metabolism of neurotransmitters in the nervous system, has an anti-stress effect. Lemongrass stimulates the respiratory and cardiac centers, increasing activity.

Natural sources of caffeine - coffee and green tea - can stimulate the central nervous system and increase blood pressure in the short term. Also, glycyrrhizin, which is contained in licorice root, has a corticosteroid-like effect, retaining sodium, thereby increasing blood pressure. Dill, ginger, basil tinctures, as mild stimulants, improve blood circulation.

The combined use of natural remedies and pharmaceutical drugs gives good results in many clinical situations. Natural remedies relieve symptoms, increase general tone and enhance the activity of the nervous system, while pharmaceutical drugs are important for quickly increasing and stabilizing blood pressure. However, some combinations require caution: for example, the simultaneous use of licorice root with fludrocortisone can excessively increase fluid retention.

In clinical practice, natural remedies are mainly helpful in mild hypotension, while pharmacological drugs are the first choice for moderate and severe cases. The combination of midodrine and fludrocortisone is the most effective in orthostatic hypotension. A comprehensive approach — including medications, natural remedies, dietary changes, and lifestyle changes — provides the best long-term management of hypotension.

Conclusion

The main goal in the treatment of hypotension is to normalize blood pressure and relieve symptoms. Pharmaceutical agents, in particular adrenomimetics (e.g., Midodrine), cardiotonics (e.g., Dopamine, Dobutamine), and mineralocorticoids (e.g., Fludrocortisone) help restore pressure by increasing vascular tone, increasing cardiac output, or increasing fluid volume. Natural remedies (adaptogenic herbs, caffeinated drinks, infusions) also help to tone the body and relieve symptoms; however, in severe cases, they should only be considered as an adjunct. To achieve the most optimal outcome, it is important to choose the

appropriate combination of pharmacological and natural approaches, taking into account the individual disease state, cause, and severity.

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